

Spectroscopy of CH₄ with a Difference Frequency Generation laser at 3.3 micron for atmospheric applications.

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Abstract The 3.25 micron spectral region is very suitable for the *in-situ* sensing of CH₄ in the troposphere and the lower stratosphere with light-weight laser sensors. Several transitions of the strong fundamental ν_3 band of CH₄ are revisited in this spectral region using an ultra compact Difference Frequency Generation (DFG) laser. Accurate intensities as well as self-broadening coefficients are reported for several manifolds that are particularly relevant to the monitoring of CH₄. The study is extended to over hundred transitions reachable over the tunability range of the laser. Moreover, this DFG laser is the light source of a new, highly-compact CH₄ laser spectrometer to be operated from weather balloon. The CH₄ laser sensor is described and preliminary results are reported.

Keywords: Methane; Atmospheric measurements; DFG spectrometer

1. Introduction

Methane is a greenhouse gas of major importance for the radiative balance of the Earth climate [1]. Methane concentration has dramatically increased by about 150% since the beginning of the industrialization era ([2]). Main sources of CH₄ are wetlands, rice paddies, anthropogenic activity as fossil fuels and ruminant animals, and biomass burning [3]. Moreover, additional methane sources due to global warming may be another threat to climate: melting permafrost may cause large methane emissions into the atmosphere [4]. In this context, the global monitoring of methane is of high importance. Purposely, we have started, with the help of the French space agency (CNES) and of the CNRS, the development of a compact CH₄ sensor to be operated from weather balloons and based on the Difference Frequency Generation (DFG) laser technology. Such laser sensors launched from a network of meteorological stations could be an excellent complement to satellite observations to achieve a global mapping of CH₄ sources and sinks. Furthermore, methane may be used as a tracer of air masses in the upper troposphere and the lower stratosphere to investigate the impact of deep convection (in the tropical regions) and of isentropic transport on stratospheric H₂O [5]. Methane is also a source of H₂O in the stratosphere (by oxidation). Therefore, this new CH₄ sensor may also be very useful to address the study of the H₂O budget in the stratosphere which is a very important issue due to the potential impact of H₂O on the radiative balance of the stratosphere and consequently on the ozone layer [6, 7, 8].

To meet these science objectives, the laser sensor weight should be of less than 5kg for the overall gondola; the *in-situ* CH₄ concentration are to be measured continuously in the troposphere and the lower stratosphere at a temporal resolution of less than 1s and with a precision error of less than 5%. The precision error can be improved by co-addition of successive measurements at the cost of a lower spatial resolution. Telecommunication laser diodes at 1.65 micron [9], lead-salt laser diode [10] or even quantum cascade lasers [11] emitting in the mid-infrared have been operated from balloons or aircrafts to monitor *in situ* CH₄ in the middle atmosphere. Due to the low concentration to be measured, these set-ups require a multi-path cell to expand the absorption path over a few tens of meters, making thereby the set-up heavy (the SDLA described in [9] has an overall weight of ~80kg) and complex to operate. To develop a light-weight laser sensor (<5kg) that can be operated even by a non-specialist, we have selected the 3.3 micron spectral region that features the strong fundamental ν_3 band of methane. Over this spectral region interband cascade laser have been implemented recently [12]. For our part, we have selected an

ultra-compact DFG laser emitting at 3.24 micron that was made available under a collaborative agreement from Novawave Technologies, Inc. **Table 1** shows the comparison between absorption depths predicted for methane in the middle atmosphere at 1.65 and at 3.24 micron. At 3.24 micron, CH₄ can be measured over 3 m instead of 50 m at 1.65 micron, thereby removing the need of an optical cell. The absorption depth expected in the stratosphere is of 1% at 20 km which is largely feasible using the direct detection technique [13].

As a first step, we have checked the emission properties of the DFG laser and we have carefully revisited the intensities and the self-broadening coefficients of CH₄ in this spectral region for three specific manifolds particularly relevant for the CH₄ laser probing. The study was then extended to over 104 methane transitions also featured over the tunability range of the DFG laser used. The first part of this paper reports the spectroscopic results. In the second part of the paper, we describe the developed balloonborne DFG laser sensor called "PicoSDLA-CH4".

2. Experimental setup

We employed a Compact Difference Frequency Generation (CDFG) laser source provided by Novawave Technologies, Inc. (USA), as part of a collaborative agreement. The CDFG emits at 3086 cm⁻¹ (3.24 μm) with a continuous coverage from 3076 to 3096 cm⁻¹ (3.23 to 3.25 μm). The set-up developed by Novawave is compact (size of approximately 20 cm x 12 cm x 2.5 cm), light weight (980 g) and it is therefore well-suited for balloonborne deployments. The line width is less than 10 MHz and the spectral emission does not feature any mode-hops over the tunability range which makes this source particularly convenient for spectroscopy. During preliminary tests, we have studied the response of the CDFG in terms of power and frequency regarding to the variations of ambient temperature. For this purpose, in our laboratory, we thermally insulate the CDFG laser module and head in a box in which we made temperature variation. We brought out a frequency shift of -0.005 cm⁻¹/Kelvin and a power variation of 2%/Kelvin regarding to ambient temperature. These tests demonstrated that temperature and power variations are low value but we thermally controlled CDFG laser module and head to avoid shift during spectroscopic measurements to have better precision. A care will be take to thermally control the CDFG laser module and head during balloonborne measurements, because of higher temperature variations that will occur with the altitude.

The temperatures of the laser diodes (signal and pump) and of the Periodically Poled Lithium Niobate (PPLN) crystal are monitored as well as the power of the lasers using a PCMCIA DAQcard-6036E, with a resolution of 16 bits and a sampling rate of 200 ks/s. An NI USB-6251 card controlled by a LabVIEW 2009 program is used to control the emission wavelength over the selected molecular line shape. The duration of the ramp and consequently of a single spectrum is of 10 ms.

Fig. 1. *Experimental setup for CH₄ intensity and self-broadening coefficients measurements on R(5), R(6) and R(7) manifolds. To avoid some frequency shift and power variation during measurement, the CDFG head and the CDFG laser module are thermally insulated in a box with Peltier controller.*

Figure 1 is a 3D-representation of the laboratory set up used to record methane spectra using the CDFG laser source. The laser beam is focused by a BaF₂ convergent lens. A ZnSe beam splitter (R=25%) is used to separate the laser beam into two parts. The first part passes through a 1.706 cm optical path length cell, and the reflected part is coupled to a confocal Fabry-Pérot interferometer (free spectral range of $9.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) to obtain relative frequency calibration. The two beams are focused on two InAs photodiodes mounted with thermistors on two-stage thermoelectric coolers from Judson. The 1.706 cm-length single path cell was used to investigate the strong manifolds R(5), R(6) and R(7). Purposely, the 1.706 cm cell was filled with low pressure (between 0.1 and 2.5 mbar) of pure methane (99.9995%). The pressure was measured with an MKS Baratron nanometer with 10 torr full scale (accuracy : 0.25%) and the temperature of the gas is measured with a Platinum PT 100 (precision error: $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$).

The spectroscopic work was then extended to numerous weak CH₄ lines that were present over the tunability range of the DFG laser. For this study, the optical path was expanded by replacing the 1.706 cm cell by a 20.4 cm long optical cell. The 20.4 cm cell was filled with 25 to

45 mbar pressure of pure methane (99.9995%). The pressure was measured with an MKS baratron nanometer with 100 torr full scale (accuracy : 0.25%). The temperature of the gas is measured with a Platinum PT 100 (precision error: $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$).

An NI USB-6251 card, with a 16 bits resolution and a 1.25 Ms/s sampling rate per channel, is used to record simultaneously 2000 sample points from the signal and Fabry-Perot channels.

3. Data processing

Signal of the spectra is recorded in volts. Remember that the transmittance, T , is the ratio between the signal after (I) and before (I_0) traversing the active media:

$$T = \frac{I}{I_0} \quad (1)$$

To obtain the transmittance from the spectra we must, therefore, calculate the ratio between the recorded signal and its base line (I_0). To obtain the base line of the spectra we fit the points far enough of the line centres to a third order polynomial. In **figure 2** we show an example of recorded spectrum and the corresponding base line given by the fit.

Fig.2. Example of experimental spectrum recorded in this work at $P = 47.423$ mbar and $T = 297.7$ K (thin line) and the corresponding base line (thick line). The last was obtained by least squares fitting to a 3 order polynome.

In the recorded methane spectra, we can observe the contribution of the atmospheric CH_4 and H_2O outside the cell. In order to eliminate these contributions, we record a spectrum with the

cell in vacuum for each one of the studied spectral regions, and we remove this contribution from the experimental spectrum.

To calibrate the spectra in terms of frequency scale, a portion of the laser beam is sent to a Fabry-Pérot interferometer (FP). The transmission of the FP is recorded simultaneously to the absorption spectrum. The distance between two consecutive maximums of transmittance of a FP is given by its Free Spectral Range (FSR). In our case, the FSR of the used FPI is 0.00945 cm^{-1} .

To obtain the absolute wave number of the spectra, we take the position of the centre of the strongest line from HITRAN database [14]. Then, we complete the wave number scale from the maximums of the FP transmission. Positions of the points between FP maximums are calculated using linear interpolation. In **figure 3** we show an example of transmission spectrum and the corresponding FP transmission. The latter is displaced for a better clarity.

Fig.3. Example of experimental spectrum of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ recorded in this work at $P = 37.970 \text{ mbar}$ and $T = 297.5 \text{ K}$, and the corresponding Fabry-Perot transmission used for the calibration of the spectrum. They have been obtained using two portions of the same laser beam, and have been recorded simultaneously.

Once the transmission spectra are calibrated in wavenumber, we obtain the absorbance, A , using the simple following relationship:

$$A = \frac{-1}{L} \ln(T) \quad (2)$$

Where L is the gas cell length. Then, the intensities and collisional broadening of the lines is obtained from the fit of the lines to a Voigt profile. In this fit, the Doppler width, γ_D , is considered as constant for the entire record, (remember that the length of each spectrum is about 1 cm^1). In **figure 4** we show an example of recorded spectrum and its corresponding Voigt fit. The residual have been displaced for the sake of clarity.

Fig.4. Example of experimental spectrum of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ recorded in this work at $P = 0.908 \text{ mbar}$ and $T = 296.8 \text{ K}$ (solid cercles), the corresponding fit to Voigt profiles (solid line) and the residual between them (open squares). Residual have been displaced for a better clarity.

Finally, the intensities, S , which were recorded at different temperatures (between 295 and 298 K), are standardized to $T = 296 \text{ K}$ using the following equation:

$$S(T_0) = S(T) \frac{Q(T)}{Q(T_0)} \exp\left[\frac{-hcE_0}{k_B} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right] \quad (3)$$

Where T_0 is the temperature of reference (296 K), k_B is the Boltzmann constant, E_0 is the energy of the lower level of the transition in cm^{-1} and Q is total internal partition sum. Q is calculated using the code described in reference [15].

4. Results and discussion

In a first step, to test the sensor, we have measured the intensities of the three manifolds R(5), R(6) et R(7) belonging to the ν_3 band and compared with those of HITRAN, which were obtained by Fourier Transform Spectroscopy (FTS) [16], and those of Pine [17], who used a difference-frequency laser spectrometer. As we can observe in **table 2**, our results are in good

agreement with both types of measurements, with a relative difference of less than 5% in the most of the cases. Only three lines of R(5) manifold present a bigger relative difference with those of HITRAN or Pine, but remember that we can observe an overlapping with atmospheric H₂O line in this part of the spectra, which complicates the determination of the base line, and therefore the determination of the intensities. We have subtracted the atmospheric contribution from our spectra to avoid problems in the determination of the base line, however no mention about that is made in any of the others two cited works, so we suppose that the reason is that this contribution has not been observed or because it has not been taken into account in the corresponding fits.

In a second step, The self-collisional broadening and intensity of 104 lines belonging to 7 different bands in the spectral interval between 3077.4 and 3094.5 cm⁻¹ have been obtained. The intensities of these lines in HITRAN come from ref [15] for the ν_1 , ν_3 , $\nu_2+\nu_4$ and $2\nu_2$ bands, and [17] for the $\nu_1+\nu_4-\nu_4$, $\nu_3+\nu_4-\nu_4$ and $\nu_2+\nu_3-\nu_2$ bands. Both of them used Fourier Transform spectrometer. In this work we present the intensities measured with difference-frequency laser spectrometer, avoiding the problem of the apparatus function determination. Concerning the self-broadening, due to a lack of experimental data, most of the values in HITRAN were obtained with a simple empirical expression [19]. In this work we present new experimental measurements of the self-broadening of the considered lines.

In total, we have studied 17 different spectral regions, 1 cm⁻¹ long (the length of one spectrum), including the three manifolds R(5), R(6) and R(7). For each of them, we have recorded between 5 – 10 spectra, which were averaged on 100 spectrums, at different pressures (0.1-2.5 mbar for the manifolds and 25–45 mbar for the rest of the lines) and temperatures varying between 295 and 298 K. All the intensity values have been however standardized at 296 K. In **table 2 and 3** we show the corresponding results. The wave numbers in the table correspond to the HITRAN line positions, and both intensity and collisional broadening are expressed in the same units as HITRAN. For each line, the experimental error is calculated as the standard error, se , giving the ratio between the standard deviation, σ , and the square root of the number of spectra, N .

and is partially absorbed *in-situ* by the ambient CH₄ molecules. A great care has been taken in the thermal protection of the CDFG laser to avoid spectral drift as the sensor will be operated in a severe environment in terms of temperature (at 10km the temperature may be as low as -70°C) and pressure (at 30km , the pressure is ~ 10hPa). As already mentioned before, we have carried out numerous tests in the laboratory to check out the behavior of the CDFG laser to changes in the ambient temperature.

Fig.6. Nomenclature of the PicoSDLA CH₄ spectrometer.

Figure 6 shows a 3D representation of the PicoSDLA-CH₄ balloonborne sensor. The laser beam of the DFG laser is collimated by a plano-convex sapphire lens. The beam passes through the open atmosphere and is reflected by a gold coating retro-reflector with a diameter of 63.5mm and shifted by 5cm. Then, the laser beam is focused by another sapphire lens to an InAs photodiode mounted with thermistors on three-stage thermoelectric coolers from Judson. The wavelength laser emission is tuned over the R(6) manifold by ramping its driving current in 10 ms. **Figure 7** is a schematic of the balloonborne spectrometer. The overall weight of the gondola's prototype is about 5 kg.

Fig.7. Schematics of the DFG sensor.

With the balloonborne version, forty 10-ms elementary spectra with 512 samples taken over each of them (16 digits sampler) will be co-added to give one measurement.

To test the prototype in **fig. 6**, we have recorded spectra of ambient air in the laboratory over the full tunability range of the DFG laser.

Fig.8. Calculated spectrum of water vapor and methane (open grey circles) and experimental spectrum (black line) from 3076 to 3096 cm^{-1} . Pressure is 1001.1 mbar, temperature is 22.8 °C, the optical path length is 355 cm.

The **fig. 8** shows the experimental spectrum of ambient air featuring methane and water vapor transitions from 3076 to 3096 cm^{-1} (black line). It consist of a juxtaposition of 16 experimental spectra of 1 cm^{-1} spectral range each. Each spectrum was obtained by applying the appropriate signal diode temperature and by ramping of the driving current over 10 ms. Grey circles represents the calculated spectrum using HITRAN 2008 database parameters for comparison.

Fig.9. Experimental spectrum of water vapor (open circles) obtained during measurements with the PicoSDLA CH_4 spectrometer. Data processing (black line) was achieved applying non-linear least square fitting procedure with Voigt profile. The humidity was recorded with Vaisala weather transmitter for comparison.

The **fig. 9** displays a zoom on the H_2O line at 3087.20 cm^{-1} in **fig. 8**. We process this spectrum by applying a Levenberg-Marquardt non-linear least square fitting with a Voigt profile. The experimental spectrum is represented with solid black line and the result of fitting procedure with open circles. To assert the reliability of our measurements we have measured simultaneously humidity, pressure and temperature with a Vaisala weather transmitter (humidity accuracy: $\pm 3\%$ RH). The mixing ratio measured by the Vaisala weather transmitter during the recording of this

spectrum was $(1.60 \pm 0.08\%)$. The mixing ratio obtain from fitting procedure is 1.64%. Both H₂O measurements are in very good agreement.

Fig.10. Absorption from our experimental spectrum (open circles) obtained by measurements for an atmospheric pressure of 1001.1 mbar and a ambient temperature of 22.1°C in our laboratory. The optical path length was 355 cm in the open atmosphere. The temperature and the pressure were measured with a Vaisala weather transmitter. We compared our transmission with a simulated transmission

including line-mixing effects (solid line) and transmission without line-mixing effects (dash line).

Figure 10 is a zoom on the R(6) manifold in figure 8. This CH₄ measurement at ground level is particularly of interest to test the detection limit of the prototype; indeed, predictions in **Table 1** permit us to estimate that the absorption depth at ground level will be of the same magnitude than the absorption depth at 20 km. This is due to the fact that the decrease in the pressure-broadening effect with altitude compensate to some extent for the decrease in the number of methane molecules; consequently, the molecular absorption depth keeps "roughly" constant from ground level to 20km. The CH₄ spectrum in **fig. 10** is the result of averaging 100 elementary 10ms-spectra (open circles). The overall averaging time is one second. We have compared the absorption of the spectrum with simulated absorption including line-mixing effects. At atmospheric pressures, line-mixing effects are of great importance in methane spectra [21]. Therefore, we have used line-mixing coefficients calculated by J.M Hartmann and H. Tran [22] (solid line). Absorption represented by dash line is a simulated without line-mixing effects (Voigt profile). The data processing of this spectrum permit us to obtain an ambient concentration of

methane of 1.98 ppmv at ground level. The agreement between line-mixing model and our experimental spectrum is better than with Voigt profile and the concentration value obtained seems in agreement with experimental conditions. Therefore, we can conclude that the detection limit is quite satisfactory. Moreover, the very good agreement between the water vapor mixing ratio measured with Vaisala weather transmitter and our spectrometer permit us to assert further the reliability of measurements.

5 Conclusion

The use of ultra compact DFG source is very promising for the development of light-weight methane laser sensors to be operated from weather balloons.

In a first step, to test the performance of the DFG source, we have made some measurements to determine the R(5), R(6) and R(7) manifolds intensities and self-broadening parameters, and compared us with HITRAN 2008 values. These spectroscopic parameters will be further used for data processing of atmospheric spectra. The results obtained are in good agreement with HITRAN values. Then, we realized a spectroscopic study covering 7 bands of methane in the spectral region from 3077 to 3095 cm^{-1} to determine the intensities and self-broadening of 104 lines. Most of the intensities have been measured by difference-frequency laser spectrometer for the first time, and we present new experimental self-broadening values for most of the lines.

In second step, a prototype of a balloonborne methane sensor based on a single path in the open atmosphere over $\sim 3\text{m}$ and using the CDFG laser has been developed. Preliminary measurements of methane and water vapor at ground level are reported to determine the detection limit. The value obtained from these *in-situ* measurements seem in good agreement with experimental conditions and demonstrate the feasibility of the monitoring at higher altitudes. Moreover, these results permit to demonstrate that we need to include line-mixing effects in our inversion code to have better precision (at least in the troposphere).

The picoSDLA CH_4 spectrometer will be deployed during two balloon campaigns. The first one in Kiruna (67°N , Sweden) in 2011, in collaboration with the CNES, for in-situ measurements of methane during polar vortex spring breakdown, and the second one, in Bauru (Brazil) in 2012, for in-situ measurements of water vapor and methane during the convective period in tropical regions.

Acknowledgements We thank Jean Michel Hartmann and Ha Tran for providing the line-mixing simulation code.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1: Experimental setup for CH₄ intensity and self-broadening coefficients measurements on R(5), R(6) and R(7) manifolds. To avoid some frequency shift and power variation during measurement, the CDFG head and the CDFG laser module are thermally insulated in a box with Peltier controllers.

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Fig. 4 : Example of experimental spectrum of ¹²CH₄ recorded in this work at $P = 0.908$ mbar and $T = 296.8$ K (solid cercles), the corresponding fit to Voigt profiles (solid line) and the residual between them (open squares). Residual have been desplaced for a better clarity.

Fig. 5: Simulated spectrum in atmospheric conditions at ground level for water vapor and methane lines on the spectral range from 3077 to 3095 cm⁻¹. The black square show the R(6) manifold selected for in-situ measurements of methane with the picoSDLA CH₄ spectrometer.

Fig. 6: Nomenclature of the PicoSDLA CH₄ spectrometer.

Fig. 7: Schematics of the DFG sensor.

Fig. 8: Calculated spectrum of water vapor and methane (open grey circles) and experimental spectrum (black line) from 3076 to 3096 cm⁻¹. Pressure is 1001.1 mbar, temperature is 22.8 °C, the optical path length is 355 cm.

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were measured with a Vaisala weather transmitter. We compared our transmission with a simulated transmission including line-mixing effects (solid line) and transmission without line-mixing effects (dash line).

Table captions

Table 1: Comparison between predicted absorption depth for the SDLA spectrometer [Durry01] (L=56m) and the picoSDLA CH₄ spectrometer (L=3.60m) in the troposphere to lower stratosphere.

Table 2: Comparison between the intensity values from the work of Pine [Pine97] (column c), HITRAN (column d) and this work (column e), for the R(5), R(6) and R(7) manifolds of the ν_3 band of ¹²CH₄. In column (a), prime and double prime refer, respectively, to upper and lower states. J is the quantum number associated with the total angular momentum, C is the quantum number corresponding to A₁, A₂, F₁, F₂ and E described in [Albert09], and α is a counting integer, increasing with energy, for levels with the same J and C. Column (b) corresponds to the HITRAN line positions. Column (f) corresponds to the relative difference between the values of the intensities obtained in this work and those of Pine. Column (g) corresponds to the relative difference between the values of the intensities obtained in this work and those of HITRAN.

Table 3: Line intensities and self-broadening of ¹²CH₄ obtained in this work. The uncertainties are standard errors. In the first column at left, prime and double prime refer, respectively, to upper and lower states. J is the quantum number associated with the total angular momentum, C is the quantum number corresponding to A₁, A₂, F₁, F₂ and E described in [Albert09], and α is a counting integer, increasing with energy, for levels with the same J and C. Line positions are those of HITRAN.

Table 1 :

Altitude (km)	P (mbar)	T (K)	ρ_{CH_4} (ppmv)	Absorption depth (%)	
				SDLA (1.65 μm)	DFG (3.24 μm)
0	1013	288.2	1.7	0.359	2.88
5	540.5	255.7	1.7	0.407	2.19
10	265	223.3	1.685	0.429	1.58
15	121.1	216.7	1.605	0.306	1.46
20	55.29	216.7	1.424	0.158	1.00
25	25.49	221.6	1.055	0.058	0.45
30	11.97	226.5	0.9136	0.024	0.21
35	5.746	236.5	0.746	0.008	0.09
40	2.871	250.4	0.5638	0.003	0.03

Table 2:

Line Brch(J'')C'C'' α' α''	Position cm ⁻¹	K _n cm ⁻¹ /molec cm ⁻² [Pine]	K _n cm ⁻¹ /molec cm ⁻² HITRAN	K _n cm ⁻¹ /molec cm ⁻² This work	Rel Diff %	Rel Diff %
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)
R(5)f2f1 α 23 α 2	3076.549659	(1.200 \pm 0.003) E-19	1.166 E-19	(1.291 \pm 0.004) E-19	7.6	10.7
R(5) ee α 1 α 1	3076.569031	(8.117 \pm 0.021) E-20	7.795 E-20	(7.000 \pm 0.048) E-20	13.8	10.2
R(5) f1f2 α 21 α 1	3076.677108	(1.195 \pm 0.003) E-19	1.156 E-19	(1.117 \pm 0.004) E-19	6.5	3.4
R(5) f2f1 α 24 α 1	3076.725178	(1.194 \pm 0.003) E-19	1.166 E-19	(1.146 \pm 0.004) E-19	4.0	1.7
R(6) a2a1 α 10 α 11	3085.862099	(1.744 \pm 0.004) E-19	1.680 E-19	(1.708 \pm 0.006) E-19	2.1	1.7
R(6) f2f1 α 25 α 11	3085.860644	(1.041 \pm 0.002) E-19	1.010 E-19	(1.029 \pm 0.004) E-19	1.2	1.9
R(6) f1f2 α 26 α 2	3085.893512	(1.043 \pm 0.002) E-19	1.010 E-19	(1.065 \pm 0.003) E-19	2.1	5.4
R(6) a1a2 α 8 α 21	3086.030714	(1.697 \pm 0.004) E-19	1.650 E-19	(1.731 \pm 0.005) E-19	2.0	4.9
R(6) f1f2 α 27 α 1	3086.071464	(1.037 \pm 0.002) E-19	9.920 E-20	(1.007 \pm 0.003) E-19	2.9	1.5
R(6) ee α 17 α 1	3086.085518	(6.917 \pm 0.015) E-20	6.620 E-20	(6.520 \pm 0.002) E-20	5.7	1.5
R(7) f2f1 α 29 α 2	3095.060894	(8.362 \pm 0.035) E-20	8.102 E-20	(8.061 \pm 0.020) E-20	3.6	0.5
R(7) ee α 20 α 1	3095.104039	(5.537 \pm 0.023) E-20	5.375 E-20	(5.405 \pm 0.053) E-20	2.4	0.6
R(7) f1f2 α 28 α 2	3095.130721	(8.333 \pm 0.035) E-20	8.042 E-20	(7.927 \pm 0.036) E-20	4.9	1.4
R(7) a1a2 α 11 α 1	3095.179340	(1.370 \pm 0.006) E-19	1.344 E-19	(1.331 \pm 0.005) E-19	2.8	1.0
R(7) f1f2 α 29 α 1	3095.351550	(8.163 \pm 0.034) E-20	7.914 E-20	(8.201 \pm 0.051) E-20	0.5	3.6
R(7) f2f1 α 30 α 1	3095.371363	(8.146 \pm 0.034) E-20	7.934 E-20	(7.889 \pm 0.035) E-20	3.2	0.6

Table 3 :

<i>Line Branche(J'')C'C''$\alpha'$$\alpha''$</i>	Position cm⁻¹	S cm⁻¹ /molecula cm⁻²	Self-Broadening cm⁻¹/atm
v₁			
R(16) a2a1 α 49 α 2	3077.58782	(1.353 \pm 0.050) E-23	0.078 \pm 0.006
v₃			
R(5) ee α 16 α 1	3079.23446	(4.153 \pm 0.439) E-23	0.053 \pm 0.008
R(5) f1f2 α 22 α 1	3079.27629	(9.728 \pm 0.161) E-23	0.060 \pm 0.007
R(5) f1f2 α 23 α 1	3080.03687	(1.267 \pm 0.005) E-21	0.096 \pm 0.003
R(5) f2f1 α 25 α 1	3080.16292	(4.875 \pm 0.177) E-22	0.057 \pm 0.020
R(5) f2f1 α 26 α 1	3083.72227	(5.156 \pm 0.045) E-22	0.101 \pm 0.002
R(5) f1f2 α 1 α 25	3084.42012	(2.079 \pm 0.068) E-23	0.070 \pm 0.004
R(5) f2f1 α 27 α 2	3084.45828	(9.655 \pm 0.083) E-23	0.107 \pm 0.002
R(6) f2f1 α 26 α 1	3088.82349	(2.793 \pm 0.032) E-23	0.053 \pm 0.004
R(6) f1f2 α 28 α 2	3088.87204	(4.215 \pm 0.037) E-23	0.084 \pm 0.001
R(6) f1f2 α 28 α 1	3088.89374	(3.081 \pm 0.070) E-23	0.075 \pm 0.002
R(6) a1a2 α 9 α 1	3089.73234	(3.307 \pm 0.002) E-21	0.111 \pm 0.007
R(6) f1f2 α 29 α 2	3089.86809	(2.293 \pm 0.029) E-22	0.109 \pm 0.014
R(6) f1f2 α 29 α 1	3089.88979	(1.161 \pm 0.012) E-21	0.139 \pm 0.027
R(6) ee α 18 α 1	3089.98981	(6.707 \pm 0.066) E-22	0.136 \pm 0.018
R(6) f1f2 α 30 α 1	3094.14584	(2.929 \pm 0.014) E-22	0.090 \pm 0.003
R(6) ee α 19 α 1	3094.21602	(2.552 \pm 0.032) E-22	0.083 \pm 0.004
v₁+v₄-v₄			
R(8) ee α 39 α 1	3092.21954	(1.148 \pm 0.011) E-23	0.059 \pm 0.002
R(8) f1f2 α 60 α 1	3092.42098	(3.187 \pm 0.046) E-23	0.088 \pm 0.003
v₃+v₄-v₄			
R(6) f2f1 α 64 α 5	3078.84180	(7.312 \pm 0.451) E-23	0.036 \pm 0.014
R(6) f2f1 α 62 α 4	3079.09110	(1.307 \pm 0.014) E-22	0.085 \pm 0.004
R(6) ee α 43 α 3	3079.18500	(9.239 \pm 0.208) E-23	0.057 \pm 0.005
R(6) f1f2 α 64 α 4	3079.22350	(1.579 \pm 0.058) E-22	0.082 \pm 0.006
R(6) f2f1 α 65 α 5	3081.86879	(6.482 \pm 3.928) E-23	0.075 \pm 0.004
R(7) f2f1 α 56 α 2	3082.31380	(1.552 \pm 0.018) E-22	0.074 \pm 0.002
R(7) ee α 37 α 1	3082.34000	(1.034 \pm 0.013) E-22	0.068 \pm 0.002
R(6) a2a1 α 24 α 2	3083.47200	(7.603 \pm 0.089) E-23	0.075 \pm 0.002
R(7) f2f1 α 61 α 3	3085.08600	(1.307 \pm 0.051) E-22	0.064 \pm 0.002
R(7) ee α 50 α 4	3087.32813	(3.793 \pm 0.060) E-23	0.067 \pm 0.002
R(7) f2f1 α 75 α 6	3087.60500	(9.760 \pm 0.108) E-23	0.089 \pm 0.001
R(7) f1f2 α 71 α 4	3087.64545	(1.185 \pm 0.014) E-22	0.081 \pm 0.002
R(7) f2f1 α 73 α 5	3087.69550	(1.301 \pm 0.005) E-22	0.116 \pm 0.003
R(6) f2f1 α 67 α 4	3088.49293	(6.927 \pm 0.444) E-24	0.121 \pm 0.019
R(8) f2f1 α 60 α 2	3091.73770	(7.062 \pm 0.302) E-24	0.058 \pm 0.005
R(7) f1f2 α 74 α 5	3091.96803	(6.532 \pm 0.169) E-24	0.052 \pm 0.004
R(7) f2f1 α 76 α 6	3092.45291	(2.916 \pm 0.062) E-23	0.085 \pm 0.004
R(8) a2a1 α 22 α 1	3093.44470	(1.379 \pm 0.009) E-22	0.081 \pm 0.002

R(7) a1a2 α 27 α 2	3093.77251	(8.993 \pm 0.145) E-23	0.081 \pm 0.007
R(8) ee α 44 α 2	3094.08340	(7.027 \pm 0.159) E-23	0.057 \pm 0.003
R(8) f1f2 α 68 α 3	3094.09700	(1.203 \pm 0.023) E-22	0.086 \pm 0.008
R(7) f1f2 α 76 α 5	3094.17668	(2.208 \pm 0.094) E-23	0.114 \pm 0.021
R(8) f2f1 α 68 α 4	3094.25175	(1.971 \pm 0.139) E-23	0.042 \pm 0.009
R(7) f2f1 α 77 α 6	3094.33882	(5.318 \pm 0.545) E-24	0.005 \pm 0.001
R(8) f1f2 α 70 α 4	3094.42929	(9.973 \pm 0.161) E-23	0.064 \pm 0.009
R(8) f2f1 α 67 α 3	3094.51237	(1.062 \pm 0.042) E-22	0.075 \pm 0.013

V₂+V₄

R(13) f2f1 α 48 α 1	3078.74288	(1.955 \pm 0.108) E-22	0.068 \pm 0.019
R(14) a2a1 α 18 α 1	3082.45932	(5.113 \pm 0.081) E-23	0.056 \pm 0.002
R(14) f2f1 α 50 α 1	3087.41754	(5.340 \pm 0.110) E-23	0.049 \pm 0.002
R(15) a2a1 α 17 α 1	3088.68712	(1.093 \pm 0.058) E-23	0.041 \pm 0.008

V₂+V₃-V₂

R(6) f2f1 α 91 α 8	3078.97055	(1.508 \pm 0.086) E-23	0.020 \pm 0.004
R(7) f1f2 α 98 α 9	3083.03211	(1.841 \pm 0.038) E-23	0.090 \pm 0.004
R(7) f2f1 α 102 α 9	3083.43125	(1.323 \pm 0.019) E-23	0.062 \pm 0.002
R(7) f2f1 α 107 α 9	3089.10193	(5.300 \pm 0.201) E-24	0.064 \pm 0.005
R(8) f1f2 α 112 α 11	3091.81422	(4.277 \pm 0.147) E-24	0.067 \pm 0.004
R(8) f2f1 α 111 α 10	3092.09696	(1.044 \pm 0.015) E-23	0.050 \pm 0.004
R(8) a1a2 α 36 α 4	3092.65306	(2.594 \pm 0.032) E-23	0.050 \pm 0.004
R(8) f2f1 α 113 α 10	3093.50015	(8.644 \pm 0.312) E-24	0.055 \pm 0.005
R(8) a2a1 α 40 α 4	3093.93073	(8.458 \pm 0.561) E-24	0.048 \pm 0.011

2v₂

Q(9) f2f1 α 40 α 3	3077.24614	(8.581 \pm 0.328) E-24	0.045 \pm 0.003
Q(7) f1f2 α 36 α 2	3077.39141	(1.342 \pm 0.006) E-22	0.088 \pm 0.003
Q(7) f1f2 α 36 α 1	3077.42951	(2.956 \pm 0.018) E-23	0.072 \pm 0.002
Q(7) ee α 23 α 1	3077.49121	(6.306 \pm 0.082) E-23	0.095 \pm 0.005
Q(10) f1f2 α 43 α 3	3077.69264	(5.838 \pm 0.274) E-24	0.041 \pm 0.005
Q(10) ee α 30 α 2	3077.77776	(8.036 \pm 0.151) E-24	0.035 \pm 0.004
Q(10) a1a2 α 16 α 1	3077.81043	(6.783 \pm 0.111) E-23	0.070 \pm 0.002
Q(10) f1f2 α 43 α 1	3077.92544	(3.098 \pm 0.114) E-23	0.069 \pm 0.006
Q(10) ee α 30 α 1	3077.99846	(1.974 \pm 0.073) E-23	0.076 \pm 0.006
Q(10) f2f1 α 46 α 2	3078.66408	(1.795 \pm 0.096) E-23	0.044 \pm 0.012
Q(8) f2f1 α 39 α 1	3078.80039	(3.234 \pm 0.246) E-22	0.042 \pm 0.014
Q(11) f2f1 α 48 α 1	3079.96464	(1.910 \pm 0.040) E-23	0.011 \pm 0.002
Q(11) f1f2 α 49 α 1	3080.00107	(3.826 \pm 0.065) E-23	0.027 \pm 0.008
Q(8) f2f1 α 40 α 2	3080.38381	(8.991 \pm 0.110) E-23	0.102 \pm 0.007
Q(8) f2f1 α 40 α 1	3080.45491	(2.190 \pm 0.050) E-23	0.093 \pm 0.023
Q(8) f1f2 α 37 α 1	3080.59528	(1.870 \pm 0.016) E-22	0.094 \pm 0.005
Q(9) f1f2 α 44 α 1	3081.78901	(2.451 \pm 0.443) E-22	0.060 \pm 0.012
Q(9) a2a1 α 16 α 1	3083.37909	(1.052 \pm 0.007) E-22	0.076 \pm 0.002
Q(12) f2f1 α 54 α 2	3083.51082	(2.124 \pm 0.029) E-23	0.105 \pm 0.007
Q(9) ee α 28 α 1	3084.10461	(9.420 \pm 0.076) E-23	0.074 \pm 0.001
Q(9) f1f2 α 45 α 2	3084.75788	(2.295 \pm 0.046) E-23	0.055 \pm 0.002

Q(9) f2f1 α 43 α 3	3084.83642	(2.675 \pm 0.072) E-23	0.056 \pm 0.002
Q(9) f2f1 α 43 α 2	3084.88622	(3.505 \pm 0.046) E-23	0.068 \pm 0.001
Q(9) a1a2 α 14 α 1	3084.91039	(3.689 \pm 0.132) E-23	0.098 \pm 0.008
Q(10) a1a2 α 17 α 1	3085.06790	(6.908 \pm 0.907) E-24	0.028 \pm 0.009
Q(10) ee α 32 α 1	3085.16882	(1.318 \pm 0.025) E-22	0.072 \pm 0.002
Q(10) f2f1 α 48 α 2	3087.06542	(7.880 \pm 0.535) E-24	0.107 \pm 0.013
Q(10) f2f1 α 48 α 1	3087.14090	(5.642 \pm 0.055) E-23	0.082 \pm 0.002
R(1) f2f1 α 13 α 1	3087.27135	(2.058 \pm 0.059) E-23	0.053 \pm 0.003
Q(11) f1f2 α 52 α 1	3088.62584	(1.414 \pm 0.006) E-22	0.063 \pm 0.001
Q(11) f2f1 α 50 α 1	3088.66712	(1.359 \pm 0.016) E-22	0.061 \pm 0.001
Q(10) f2f1 α 49 α 2	3088.73717	(1.506 \pm 0.021) E-23	0.043 \pm 0.003
Q(10) f1f2 α 47 α 3	3088.75344	(1.167 \pm 0.058) E-23	0.056 \pm 0.007
Q(10) f2f1 α 49 α 1	3088.81265	(2.932 \pm 0.067) E-23	0.050 \pm 0.005
Q(10) a2a1 α 15 α 1	3089.00506	(9.688 \pm 0.080) E-23	0.073 \pm 0.001
Q(15) f2f1 α 64 α 1	3089.05790	(2.073 \pm 0.105) E-24	0.015 \pm 0.004
Q(11) ee α 34 α 1	3091.10960	(2.632 \pm 0.039) E-23	0.058 \pm 0.002
Q(11) f1f2 α 53 α 3	3091.12366	(6.477 \pm 0.371) E-24	0.117 \pm 0.009
Q(11) f1f2 α 53 α 2	3091.26439	(4.354 \pm 0.033) E-23	0.083 \pm 0.001
Q(12) ee α 37 α 1	3092.34862	(4.834 \pm 0.165) E-24	0.032 \pm 0.006
Q(12) f2f1 α 56 α 1	3092.36224	(7.653 \pm 0.192) E-23	0.052 \pm 0.004
Q(12) a2a1 α 18 α 1	3092.39015	(1.405 \pm 0.009) E-22	0.061 \pm 0.001
Q(11) f1f2 α 54 α 3	3092.55533	(8.544 \pm 0.388) E-24	0.056 \pm 0.005
Q(11) f1f2 α 54 α 2	3092.69603	(1.817 \pm 0.070) E-23	0.038 \pm 0.009
Q(11) ee α 35 α 2	3093.04635	(3.464 \pm 0.153) E-24	0.010 \pm 0.001
Q(11) f2f1 α 52 α 2	3093.27684	(3.937 \pm 0.027) E-23	0.093 \pm 0.004
